

ACUTE EFFECTS OF ANAEROBIC EXERCISE WITH DIFFERENT INTENSITIES ON DYNAMIC BALANCE PERFORMANCE

Maan Hasan Mahmood^{1*}, Mustafa Özdal¹,
Muhammet Hakan Mayda², Mürsel Biçer¹

¹Gaziantep University,
Physical Education and Sport Department,
Gaziantep, Turkey

²Ondokuz Mayıs University,
Yasar Dogu Sport Science Faculty,
Samsun, Turkey

Abstract:

The purpose of this study was to investigate of acute effects of anaerobic exercise at different intensities on dynamic balance performance. Twenty sedentary men who were 23.70 ± 1.45 years old, were voluntarily participated in the study. Single-blind, randomized controlled crossover design was used as experimental design. For determining dynamic balance, dynamic balance test on isokinetic balance device with dominant-single-leg test procedure was used. To create anaerobic exercise effect, Wingate anaerobic power test was used with different loads. Dynamic balance performance was measured one time before anaerobic exercise trials. During the following four days, anaerobic exercise trials with different intensities were applied in order to create anaerobic acute effect. Dynamic balance test procedure immediately applied after all anaerobic trials. For analyzing obtained data, repeated measures analysis of variance and LSD correction tests were applied. In terms of other trials, 10.0% and 7.5% anaerobic exercise trials showed significant decrement in overall and anterior-posterior balance points ($p < 0.05$). In terms of other trials, 10.0%, 7.5%, and 5.0% anaerobic exercise trials showed significant decrement in medial-lateral balance point ($p < 0.05$). Besides, balance points increased in 10.0% trial, while the balance points gradually decreased to 7.5% trial from control. In summary, it could be said that dynamic balance positively influenced from anaerobic exercise when it low intensity, and negatively influenced from anaerobic exercise when it high intensity.

* Correspondence: email ma3an.hassan@gmail.com

Keywords: assessment, formative assessment, summative assessment, instructors, higher education

1. Introduction

The balance can be defined as the ability to maintain a base of support with minimal movement and the ability to perform a task while maintaining a stable position, as dynamic (Grigg, 1994; Palmieri et al., 2003; Palmieri et al., 2002). The balance is appointed at performing sportive skills, initial movements, locomotor moves, and multidimensional moves of subjects, trunk stabilization, and sportive performance (James et al., 2001). These highlighted features show importance of balance for athletic performance.

The balance can be affected from some factors as biomechanical and physiological. The others are dominant leg, exercise history, age, height, weight, physical activity level, injuries and fatigue (Rozzi et al., 1999). The fatigue is one of important factors on the balance (Sato and Mokha, 2009). Researches well-clearly presented the balance could be negatively affected from the fatigue (Johnston et al., 1998; Yaggie and McGregor, 2002; Nardone et al., 1997; Wilkins et al., 2004; Gosselin et al., 2004; Frzovic et al., 2000; Adlerton and Moritz, 1996; Bellew and Fenter, 2006). But it is not known how the effects of the intensity level of anaerobic physical activity on dynamic balance.

There are no studies about effects of the different loads of anaerobic physical activity on dynamic balance. It could be hypothesized that the increased anaerobic intensity affects the dynamic balance. The present study aimed to investigate the effect of the anaerobic exercise intensities on the dynamic balance performance.

2. Method

2.1 Experimental Design

The present study was designed as single-blind, randomized, trial-controlled repeated measures design. The subjects visited laboratory six times. During the first visit, they were familiarized with the dynamic balance test and anaerobic exercise protocol, and they signed the written consent. During the second visit, the descriptive data were recorded and the "control trial" that included only dynamic balance test without anaerobic exercise. The third, fourth, fifth, and sixth visits included dynamic balance test after anaerobic exercises with 2.5%, 5.0%, 7.5%, 10.0% loads, randomly. The trials were performed at the same time (10:00-12:00), with 24 hour rest bouts.

2.2 Subjects

Twenty sedanter males participated in the study voluntarily (Table 1). The mean age of subjects is 23.70 ± 1.45 year. The inclusion criterias are having without sportive history, non-participant in regular physical activity, and no have diagnosed disease. Written consent from subjects and ethical approval from Gaziantep Clinical Research Ethical Committee were received (2016-283).

Table 1: Descriptive parameters of subjects (N = 20)

	Mean	S.D.
Age (year)	23.70	1.45
Height (cm)	178.40	6.98
Weight (kg)	74.50	9.65
BMI (kg/m ²)	23.33	1.95
BFP (%)	15.75	4.30
Overall balance (point)	2.14	0.76
Anterior-posterior balance (point)	1.55	0.63
Medial-lateral balance (point)	1.54	0.73

SD, standard deviation; BMI, body mass index; BFP, body fat percentage (note that, BFP was calculated with Yuhasz formula)

2.3 Procedures

2.3.1 Dynamic Balance Measurement

A mechanized balance system (Biodex Balance SD, Biodex Inc., NY, USA) used for measuring ODB. The platform setting set at fourth level. The testing protocol consisted of three 20-second (between 10-second rest) with dominant one-legged on dynamic unstable surface. Subjects stood on their dominant leg on the balance platform. The platform was then unlocked to allow motion. Subjects were instructed to adjust the position of the supporting foot until they found a position where they could maintain platform stability. Then, the platform was locked and testing began as the platform was released for a 20-sec trial and participants were asked to maintain an upright standing position on their dominant limb. The unsupported leg was in a comfortable knee-flexed position. For the trial to be complete, balance needed to be maintained for 20 sec. The handrails to the BBS were up only between trials and participants were permitted to move their arms to assist in maintaining balance. Testing was repeated for three trials between 10-sec rest (Cachupe et al., 2001). Overall balance, anterior-posterior balance, medial-lateral balance values were obtained via the test. The value is the better the closer to zero.

2.3.2 Anaerobic Exercise Procedures

Anaerobic exercise for lower extremities was applied with cycle ergometer (894E Peak Bike, Monark Exercise AB, Vansbro, Sweden) and Wingate test procedure. Before exercise, cycle seat and handle bar was adjusted for each subject. Resistance load was set at 2.5%, 5.0%, 7.5%, 10.0%, randomly for trials, of subject's body weight. The subjects performed warm-up approximately 5-10 minutes. When subject felt warming up, seated to cycle and pressed to cycle button for drop load. After than subject pedaled as fast as possible while seated for 30 seconds. During 30 seconds exercise time, operator provided verbal encouragement to maximal effort of subject (Bar-Or, 1987; Taşmektepligil et al., 2012).

2.3.3 Statistical Method

For statistical analysis, SPSS 22.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, Il) was used. Data are presented as mean, standard deviation, and the mean percent of difference. The Shapiro–Wilk test was used for normality. In order to determine the significant effects of the anaerobic exercise trials on the dynamic balance, repeated measures one way ANOVA and LSD tests were performed. Significance was defined as $p \leq 0.05$.

3. Results

There were significant differences between trials in the overall balance (Table 2). LSD test showed that significant differences were found between 10.0% trial and control trial; 7.5% trial and 2.5%, control trials; 5.0% trial and 2.5%, control trials ($p < 0.05$).

Table 2: Overall balance analysis

Trial	Mean (point)	S.D.	f	p	Significant difference
A. Control	2.14	0.76			
B. 2.5%	2.07	0.80			E-A
C. 5.0%	1.50	0.55	13.892	0.001	D-A; D-B
D. 7.5%	1.47	0.71			C-A; C-B
E. 10.0%	1.59	0.63			

Note: The value is the better the closer to zero.

Table 3 shows anterior-posterior balance alteration between the trials. There were significant differences between the trials in the anterior-posterior balance. LSD test showed that significant differences were found between 10.0% trial and control trial; 7.5% trial and 2.5%, control trials; 5.0% trial and 2.5%, control trials ($p < 0.05$).

Table 3: Anterior-posterior balance analysis

Trial	Mean (point)	S.D.	f	p	Significant difference
A. Control	1.55	0.63			
B. 2.5%	1.38	0.65			
C. 5.0%	1.16	0.66	3.787	0.007	E-A D-A; D-B
D. 7.5%	1.06	0.50			C-A; C-B
E. 10.0%	1.29	0.49			

Note: The value is the better the closer to zero.

Table 4 shows medial-lateral balance change between the trials. There were significant differences between the trials in the medial-lateral balance. LSD test showed that significant differences were found between 10.0% trial and 2.5%, control trials; 7.5% trial and 2.5%, control trials; 5.0% trial and 2.5%, control trials ($p < 0.05$).

Table 4: Medial-lateral balance analysis

Trial	Mean (point)	S.D.	f	p	Significant difference
A. Control	1.54	0.73			
B. 2.5%	1.35	0.76			E-A; E-B
C. 5.0%	0.84	0.31	4.271	0.001	D-A; D-B C-A; C-B
D. 7.5%	0.79	0.39			B-A
E. 10.0%	0.93	0.53			

Note: The value is the better the closer to zero.

The balance performance showed increment from the control trial to 7.5% trial in all the balance parameters. The performance increment understood from decrement the balance values as numerical. But after 10.0% trial balance performance started to impairment (Figure 1). The performance decrement understood from increment the balance values as numerical.

Figure 1: Difference of balance performance between trials

4. Discussion

Different intensities of anaerobic exercise were performed before dynamic balance test in the present study. According to obtained data, significant differences were found between 10.0% trial and control trial; 7.5% trial and 2.5%, control trials; 5.0% trial and 2.5%, control trials in the overall and anterior-posterior balance values ($p < 0.05$). Also, significant differences between the trials in the anterior-posterior balance. LSD test showed that significant differences were found between 10.0% trial and 2.5%, control trials; 7.5% trial and 2.5%, control trials; 5.0% trial and 2.5%, control trials in the medial-lateral balance ($p < 0.05$).

The overall balance was measured in the control trial by 2.14 ± 0.76 point, in the 2.5% trial by 2.07 ± 0.80 point, in the 5.0% trial by 1.50 ± 0.55 point, in the 7.5% trial by 1.47 ± 0.71 point, in the 10.0% trial by 1.59 ± 0.63 point. The anterior-posterior balance was observed in the control, 2.5%, 5.0%, 7.5%, and 10.0% trials by 1.55 ± 0.63 point, 1.38 ± 0.65 point, 1.16 ± 0.66 point, 1.06 ± 0.50 point, 1.29 ± 0.49 point, respectively. The medial-lateral balance was measured in the control, 2.5%, 5.0%, 7.5%, and 10.0% trials by 1.54 ± 0.73 point, 1.35 ± 0.76 point, 0.84 ± 0.31 point, 0.79 ± 0.39 point, 0.93 ± 0.53 point, respectively.

Additionally, the balance performance showed increment from the control trial to 7.5% trial in all the balance parameters. But after 10.0% trial balance performance started to decrement. This result important to explain importance of the study.

A previous study presented the moderate intensity of exercise may have a positive effect on the balance performance (Schneiders et al, 2012). However the high intensity of exercise can be a reason of the decrement in balance performance (Schneiders et al, 2012; Erkmen et al., 2009; Bove et al., 2005; Susco et al., 2004; Wilkins et al., 2004; Waterman et al., 2004; Erkmen et al., 2009). Researches showed that the most important factor of the reason on decrement in balance performance is fatigue in lower extremity (Yaggie and McGregor, 2002; Surenkok et al, 2006), rather than fatigue in upper extremity (Surenkok et al, 2008).

In the present study, 10.0% trial caused a marked decrement in balance performance, and it can be concluded that fatigue is a reason of this result. It is known that fatigue in lower extremity can be caused increased swing level in anterior-posterior direction. As a result of this, it may be considered that production of efferent signal which is required for body stability may be reduced, because transmission of afferent signal may be declined by fatigue (Gribble and Hertel, 2004; Gribble et al, 2004; Nardone et al., 1997; Johnston et al., 1998). Additionally, muscle fatigue can be caused decrement in proprioceptive and kinesthetic properties in joints. Due to reduced afferent signal transmission following fatigue, the muscle spindle discharge threshold could increase, resulting in a change in joint sensitivity (Rozzi et al., 1999).

In the present study, fatigue in the 10.0% trial may be peripheral/muscular (Holtzhausen and Noakes, 1995; Douglas et al., 1987; Douglas et al, 1998; Lomax et al., 2015; Lomax et al., 2014). During exercise alteration in cardiovascular (Holtzhausen and Noakes, 1995; Douglas et al., 1987;), endocrinal (Douglas et al, 1998) that occurred in muscle glycogen stores after high intensity exercise (Çinar et al., 2010), energy metabolism (Laursen et al., 2002; Mendes, 2016; Akcan and Biçer, 2015), and related with homeostasis (Çinar et al., 2008) could be occurred by fatigue, and the reasons above may be affect the body swing (Ledin et al., 2004; Vuillerme et al., 2002; Caron, 2003; Vuillerme et al., 2006; Vuillerme and Demetz, 2007). Proprioceptive and exteroceptive information system and their integration may be affected by high intensity exercise, and muscular activity may be decrease. After that motor-neuron output of type III and IV muscular afferents reduce, thus the ability to catch the same angle of lower extremity could be negatively affect (Nardone et al., 1997; Lepers et al., 1997; Gauchard et al., 2002). As a result of these factors, kinesthetic awareness and motor control could be decrease (Walsh et al., 2004).

In addition to the above information, high intensity exercise caused to acidosis and deep ventilation, and this result caused to increased body swing (Hunter and Kearney, 1981; Jeong, 1991; Bouisset and Duchêne, 1994; Sakellari et al., 1997). Besides, the situation of fatigue is not only occurred on muscular level, it also occurs at central

nervous system and caused deficiency motor-drive. Therefore the reduction and deterioration of the expected return from the sense of joint position are the main effects (Gandevia, 2001; Lepers et al., 1997; Seliga et al., 1991; Forestier et al., 2002).

In the present study, 5.0% and 7.5% trials show improve in balance performance. This result cannot be explain with fatigue effect, but can be explain with warm-up effect. Muscular temperature and contractional ability-strength of muscle can be increase with warming up (McConnell et al., 1997). Warm up caused to decrement in joint and muscle stiffness (Wright and Johns, 1961; Proske et al., 1993), increased nerve signal speed (Karvonen and Lemon, 1992), improved power-acceleration relation (Ranatunga et al., 1987), and increased glycolysis-phosphate degradation (Febbraio et al., 1996), improved coordination of inter-intramuscular (Özdal, 2015; Özdal, 2016a; 2016b; 2016c; Özdal et al., 2016).

As a result, it could be said that moderate anaerobic exercise may positively affect the dynamic balance performance due to warm-up effect; however high intensity may negatively affect the dynamic balance ability due to fatigue effect.

References

1. Adlerton AK, Moritz U. Does calf-muscle fatigue affect standing balance?. *Scandinavian Journal of Medicine & Science in Sports*. 1996;6(4):211-215.
2. Akcan F, Biçer M. The effect of two different strength training programs applied to male athletes in the various branches on some physical and physiological parameters. *Turkish Journal of Sport and Exercise*. 2015;17(2):1-7.
3. Bar-Or O. The Wingate anaerobic test an update on methodology, reliability and validity. *Sports Med*, 1987, 4(6), 381-394.
4. Bellew JW, Fenter PC. Control of balance differs after knee or ankle fatigue in older women. *Archives of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation*, 2006;87(11):1486-1489.
5. Bouisset S, Duchêne JL. Is body balance more perturbed by respiration in seating than in standing posture? *Neuroreport*, 1994;5(8):957-960.
6. Bove M, Brunori A, Cogo C, Faelli E, Ruggeri P. Effects of a fatiguing treadmill exercise on body balance. *Gait & Posture*. 2005;21:121.
7. Cachupe WJ, Shifflett B, Kahanov L, Wughalter EH. Reliability of biodex balance system measures. *Measurement in Physical Education and Exercise Science*. 2001; 5(2): 97-108.

8. Caron O. Effects of local fatigue of the lower limbs on postural control and postural stability in standing posture. *Neuroscience Letters*, 2003;340(2):83-86.
9. Çınar V, Mogulkoc R, Baltaci AK, Bostanci O. Effects of calcium supplementation on glucose and insulin levels of athletes at rest and after exercise. *Biological Trace Element Research*. 2010;133(1):29-33.
10. Çınar V, Mogulkoc R, Baltaci AK, Polat Y. Adrenocorticotrophic hormone and cortisol levels in athletes and sedentary subjects at rest and exhaustion: effects of magnesium supplementation. *Biological Trace Element Research*. 2008;121(3):215-20.
11. Douglas PS, O'Toole ML, Hiller WD, Hackney K, Reichel N. Cardiac fatigue after prolonged exercise. *Circulation*, 1987;76(6):1206-1213.
12. Douglas PS, O'toole ML, Katz SE. Prolonged exercise alters cardiac chronotropic responsiveness in endurance athletes. *The Journal of Sports Medicine and Physical Fitness*, 1998;38(2):158-163.
13. Erkmen N, Taşkın H, Kaplan T, Sanioğlu A. The effect of fatiguing exercise on balance performance as measured by the balance error scoring system. *Isokinetics and Exercise Science*, 2009;17(2):121-127.
14. Erkmen N, Taşkın H, Sanioğlu A, Kaplan T. Futbolcularda yorgunluğun denge performansına etkisi. *E-Journal of New World Sciences Academy Sport Sciences*. 2009;4(4):289-99.
15. Febbraio MA, Carey MF, Snow RJ, Stathis CG, Hargreaves M. Influence of elevated muscle temperature on metabolism during intense, dynamic exercise. *Am J Physiol Regul Integr Comp Physiol*. 1996;271(5):R1251-R1255.
16. Forestier N, Teasdale N, Nougier V. Alteration of the position sense at the ankle induced by muscular fatigue in humans. *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise*, 2002;34(1):117-122.
17. Frzovic D, Morris ME, Vowels L. Clinical tests of standing balance: performance of persons with multiple sclerosis. *Archives of physical medicine and rehabilitation*, 200;81(2):215-221.
18. Gandevia SC. Spinal and supraspinal factors in human muscle fatigue. *Physiological Reviews*, 2001;81(4):1725-1789.
19. Gauchard GC, Gangloff P, Vouriot A, Mallie JP, Perrin PP. Effects of exercise-induced fatigue with and without hydration on static postural control in adult human subjects. *International Journal of Neuroscience*, 2002;112(10):1191-206.
20. Gosselin G, Rassoulain H, Brown I. Effects of neck extensor muscles fatigue on balance. *Clinical Biomechanics*, 2004;19(5):473-479.

21. Gribble PA, Hertel J, Denegar CR, Buckley WE. The effects of fatigue and chronic ankle instability on dynamic postural control. *Journal of Athletic Training*, 2004;39(4):321-326.
22. Gribble PA, Hertel J. Effect of lower-extremity muscle fatigue on postural control. *Archives of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation*, 2004;85(4):589-592.
23. Grigg P. Peripheral neural mechanisms in proprioception. *J Sport Rehabil*. 1994;3:2-17.
24. Holtzhausen LM, Noakes TD. The prevalence and significance of post-exercise (postural) hypotension in ultramarathon runners. *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise*, 1995;27(12):1595-1601.
25. Hunter IW, Kearney RE. Respiratory components of human postural sway. *Neuroscience Letters*, 1981;25(2):155-159.
26. James AA, Edward M, Laura J. Can Proprioception Really Be Improved By Exercises? *Knee Surg, Sports Traumatol, Arthrosc*, 2001;9:128-136.
27. Jeong BY. Respiration effect on standing balance. *Arch Phys Med Rehabil*, 1991;72(9):642-645.
28. Johnston RB, Howard ME, Cawley PW, Losse GM. Effect of lower extremity muscular fatigue on motor control performance. *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise*, 1998;30(12):1703-1707.
29. Karvonen J, Lemon PWR. *Medicine in Sports Training and Coaching*. Basel, Karger Pub.1992:190-213.
30. Laursen PB, Rhodes EC, Langill RH, McKenzie DC, Taunton JE. Relationship of exercise test variables to cycling performance in an Ironman triathlon. *European Journal of Applied Physiology*, 2002;87(4):433-440.
31. Ledin T, Fransson PA, Magnusson M. Effects of postural disturbances with fatigued triceps surae muscles or with 20% additional body weight. *Gait & Posture*, 2004;19(2):184-193.
32. Lepers R, Bigard AX, Diard JP, Gouteyron JF, Guezennec CY. Posture control after prolonged exercise. *European Journal of Applied Physiology and Occupational Physiology*, 1997;76(1):55-61.
33. Lomax M, Tasker L, Bostanci O. An electromyographic evaluation of dual role breathing and upper body muscles in response to front crawl swimming. *Scandinavian Journal of Medicine & Science in Sports*. 2015;25(5).
34. Lomax M, Tasker L, Bostanci O. Inspiratory muscle fatigue affects latissimus dorsi but not pectoralis major activity during arms only front crawl sprinting. *The Journal of Strength & Conditioning Research*. 2014;28(8):2262-9.

35. McConnell AK, Caine MP, Sharpe GR. Inspiratory muscle fatigue following running to volitional fatigue: The influence of baseline strength. *Int J Sports Med*, 1997;18(3):169-173.
36. Mendeş B. The effects of core training applied to footballers on anaerobic power, speed and agility performance. *Anthropologist*. 2016;23(3):361-6.
37. Nardone A, Tarantola J, Giordano A, Schieppati M. Fatigue effects on body balance. *Electroencephalography and Clinical Neurophysiology / Electromyography and Motor Control*, 1997;105(4):309-320.
38. Özdal M, Bostanci Ö, Dağlioğlu Ö, Ağaoğlu SA, Kabadayi M. Effect of respiratory warm-up on anaerobic power. *Journal of Physical Therapy Science*. 2016;28(7):2097-2098.
39. Özdal M. Acute effects of aerobic and two different anaerobic exercises on respiratory muscle strength of well-trained men. *European Journal of Sport and Exercise Science*, 2015;4(4):7-12.
40. Özdal M. Acute effects of inspiratory muscle warm-up on pulmonary function in healthy subjects. *Respiratory Physiology & Neurobiology*, 2016c;227:23-26.
41. Özdal M. Effect of core training on inspiratory muscle strength in welltrained men. *Journal of Biology of Exercise*, 2016a;12(1):23-32.
42. Özdal M. Influence of an eight-week core strength training program on respiratory muscle fatigue following incremental exercise. *Isokinetics and Exercise Science*, 2016b;24:225-230.
43. Palmieri RM, Ingersoll CD, Cordova ML, Kinzey SJ, Stone MB, Krause BA. The effect of a simulated knee joint effusion on postural control in healthy subjects. *Arch Phys Med Rehabil*. 2003;84:1076-1079.
44. Palmieri RM, Ingersoll CD, Stone MB, Krause BA. Center-of-pressure parameters used in the assessment of postural control. *J Sport Rehabil*. 2002;11:51-66.
45. Proske U, Morgan DL, Gregory JE. Thixotropy in skeletal muscle and in muscle spindles: a review. *Prog Neurobiol*. 1993;41(6):705-721.
46. Ranatunga KW, Sharpe B, Turnbull B. Contractions of human skeletal muscle at different temperatures. *J Physiol*. 1987;390(1):383-395.
47. Rozzi SL, Lephart SM, Fu FH. Effects of muscular fatigue on knee joint laxity and neuromuscular characteristics of male and female athletes. *Journal of Athletic Training*, 1999;34(2):106-114.
48. Rozzi SL, Lephart SM, Gear WS. Knee Joint Laxity and Neuromuscular Characteristics of Male And Female Soccer and Basketball Players, *The American Journal Of Sports Medicine*, 1999; 27: 312-319.

49. Sakellari V, Bronstein AM, Corna S, Hammon CA, Jones S, Wolsley CJ. The effects of hyperventilation on postural control mechanisms. *Brain*, 1997;120(9):1659-1673.
50. Sato K, Mokha M. Does core strength training influence running kinetics, lower-extremity stability, and 5000-M performance in runners? *J Strength Cond Res*. 2009; 23(1): 133-140.
51. Schneiders AG, Sullivan SJ, Handcock P, Gray A, McCrory PR. Sports concussion assessment: the effect of exercise on dynamic and static balance. *Scandinavian Journal of Medicine & Science in Sports*. 2012;22(1):85-90.
52. Seliga R, Bhattacharya A, Succop P, Wickstrom R, Smith D, Willeke K. Effect of work loan and respirator wear on postural stability, heart rate, and perceived exertion. *The American Industrial Hygiene Association Journal*, 1991;52(10):417-422.
53. Surenkok O, Isler AK, Aytar A, Gultekin Z, Akman MN. Effect of knee muscle fatigue and lactic acid accumulation on balance in healthy subjects. *Isokinetics and Exercise Science*, 2006;14(4):301-306.
54. Surenkok O, Kin-Isler A, Aytar A, Gültekin Z. Effect of trunk-muscle fatigue and lactic acid accumulation on balance in healthy subjects. *Journal of Sport Rehabilitation*, 2008;17(4):380-386.
55. Susco TM, McLeod TC, Gansneder BM, Shultz SJ. Balance recovers within 20 minutes after exertion as measured by the Balance Error Scoring System. *Journal of athletic training*. 2004;39(3):241-246.
56. Taşmektepligil MY, Ozkaya O, Kabadayı M, Kuzucu OE. Mechanical and physiological responses of two different anaerobic test modalities. *Isokinetics and Exercise Science*. 2012;20(1):37-9.
57. Vuillerme N, Burdet C, Isableu B, Demetz S. The magnitude of the effect of calf muscles fatigue on postural control during bipedal quiet standing with vision depends on the eye–visual target distance. *Gait & Posture*, 2006;24(2):169-172.
58. Vuillerme N, Danion F, Forestier N, Nougier V. Postural sway under muscle vibration and muscle fatigue in humans. *Neuroscience Letters*, 2002;333(2):131-135.
59. Vuillerme N, Demetz S. Do ankle foot orthoses modify postural control during bipedal quiet standing following a localized fatigue of the ankle muscles? *International Journal of Sports Medicine*, 2007;28(03):243-246.
60. Walsh LD, Hesse CW, Morgan DL, Proske U. Human forearm position sense after fatigue of elbow flexor muscles. *The Journal of Physiology*, 2004;558(2):705-715.

61. Waterman N, Sole G, Hale L. The effect of a netball game on parameters of balance. *Physical Therapy in Sport*, 2004;5(4):200-207.
62. Wilkins JC, McLeod TC, Perrin DH, Gansneder BM. Performance on the balance error scoring system decreases after fatigue. *Journal of athletic training*. 2004;39(2):156-161.
63. Wright V, Johns RJ. Quantitative and qualitative analysis of joint stiffness in normal subjects and in patients with connective tissue disease. *Ann Rheum Dis*, 1961;20(1):36-46.
64. Yaggie JA, McGregor SJ. Effects of isokinetic ankle fatigue on the maintenance of balance and postural limits. *Archives of physical Medicine and Rehabilitation*, 2002;83(2):224-228.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Education Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).